

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

No 3(25)

27.03.2025

IF 2024
11.7

RTADQIQ VA TATBIQ

Research and implementation

scientific-methodical journal

SCIENCE S

Exact, Natural, Political, Social, Economic, Technical, Medical, Pedagogical

ISSN INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

rai-journal.uz

[@ferteach_uz](https://twitter.com/ferteach_uz)

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Uzbek, Russian, English and
Karakalpak

Registered in the Agency of
Information and Mass
Communications under the
Administration of the
President of the Republic of
Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023
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Ko'krak bezi saratoni kasalligi profilaktikasida immunitetning roli

Jalilova Xadicha Akbarovna, Alijonov Axror Nodir o'g'li

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Annotatsiya . Ushbu maqolada ko'krak bezi saratoni kasalligining kelib chiqish sabablari, tarqalishi, rivojlanish mexanizmlari va bosqichlari haqida so'z boradi. Immunitet tizimining vazifalari va saraton hujayralariga qarshi kurash, immunitet va ko'krak bezi saratoni bilan bog'liq bo'lgan jarayonlar ya'ni immunitetning zaiflashishi va immun nazorati ahamiyati bayon qilingan. Uy sharoitida maxalliy dorivor o'simliklar bilan immunitetni mustahkamlash usullari haqida tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Saraton, stress, vaksinatсия, immunoterapiya, estrogen, BRSA1, BRSA2 genlar.

Роль иммунитета в профилактике рака молочной железы

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются причины, распространение, механизмы и стадии рака молочной железы. Описываются функции иммунной системы и борьба с раковыми клетками, процессы, связанные с иммунитетом и раком молочной железы, а именно значение иммуносупрессии и иммунного контроля. Даны рекомендации по способам укрепления иммунитета местными лекарственными растениями в домашних условиях.

Ключевые слова: Рак, стресс, вакцинация, иммунотерапия, эстроген, гены BRSA1, BRSA2.

The Role of Immunity in Breast Cancer Prevention

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Students of Andijan branch of Kokand University

Annotation. This article discusses the causes, spread, mechanisms and stages of breast cancer. The functions of the immune system and the fight against cancer cells, the processes associated with immunity and breast cancer, namely the importance of immune suppression and immune control, are described. Recommendations are given on ways to strengthen immunity with local medicinal plants at home.

Keywords: Cancer, stress, vaccination, immunotherapy, estrogen, BRSA1, BRSA2 genes.

Kirish . Ko'krak bezi saratoni ayollar orasida eng ko'p uchraydigan onkologik kasalliklardan biri bo'lib, uning profilaktikasi sog'liqni saqlash tizimida muhim ahamiyatga ega . Jaxon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti (JSST) bergan ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, ko'krak bezi saratoni uchragan bemorlar soni Evropada (yiliga 180 000 ta holat) va AQSHda (yiliga 130 000 dan ortiq) ni tashqil qiladi. Ushbu kasallik bilan kasallanishning eng katta o'sishi Kanada, AQSH, Shvetsiya, Ispaniya va Finlyandiyada kuzatilmoqda. Saraton kasalligiga chalinganlarning soni 2000 yilda 10 000 000 ni tashkil etdi. Ekologik omil va turmush tarzi yomonlashib borayotganligi sababli 2020 yilga kelib olimlar aytishiga ko'ra saraton bilan kasallanganlar soni 16 000 000 deb tahmin qilishmoqda (Murodxo'jayev N va boshq. 2002).

Eng kam holatlar Yaponiyada uchraydi, bu yerda ko'krak bezi saratoni har 100 000 ayolga atiga 12-15 holatda uchraydi. Sharqiy Evropada har 100 000 ayolga 40-60 holat to'g'ri keladi. Butun dunyo olimlarining ma'lumotiga ko'ra yer yuzida aniqlanadigan ko'krak bezi saraton kasalligining 85-90% ni ayollarning o'zlari o'z-o'zini tekshirish usuli bilan aniqlanar ekan. 10-15% ni shifokorlar aniqlar ekan (Чиссов В. 2007). Quyida odam organizmida hosil bo'luvchi o'smalarning xususiyatlari o'zaro taqqoslangan jadval keltirilgan:

O'sma turlari va ularning xususiyatlari					
Yaxshi	sifatli	o'sma	Yomon	sifatli	o'sma
xususiyatlari			xususiyatlari		
Kapsulaga ega bo'ladi			Kapsulaga ega bo'lmaydi		
Ekspansiv o'sish			Ekspansiv bo'lmagan o'sish		
Yuqori darajada kodlashgan			Yuqori darajada kodlashmagan		
Kam mitoz			Ko'p mitoz		
Sekin o'sadi			Tez o'sadi		
Metastaz bermasligi			Metastaz beradi		

Kuzatishlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ko'pincha ayollarda tuximdonlar faoliyati buzilishi tufayli qonda estrogenlar miqdori oshadi, sut bezi epiteliysi va biriktiruvchi to'qimasining o'choqli proliferasiyasi va atipik hujayralar paydo bo'lishi mumkun. Ma'lumki kasallik asosan tug'magan yoki kam tuqqan, ko'p marta homladorlikni to'xtatish (abort) qildirgan, tuximdonlarning surunkali shamollash kasalliklari bilan og'riydigan, hayiz ko'rish 13 yoshdan oldin boshlanib 50 yoshdan keyin to'xtagan, bolasini emizmagani ayollarda ko'proq kuzatiladi.

Ovqatlanish tartibining buzilishi ham ma'lum darajada ahamiyatga ega. Vazni ortib ketgan, ko'p miqdorda yog'li ovqatlar, vitamin beta - karotinoidlar miqdori kam bo'lgan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini iste'mol qiladigan xotin- qizlarda ham sut bezi raki bilan kasallanish ehtimoli ko'p bo'ladi (Asqarov I. 2024). Sut bezi saraton oldi kasalliklari ayollar organizmida sodir bo'ladigan gormonal buzilishlar avvaliga mastopatiya (Ганцев III. 2006).

Yana bir turi sut bezlari yo'li Papillomasi (qon oqib turgan sut bezi) deyiladi. Bu kasallikda emchak uchiga yaqin teri ostidagi sut yo'llari ichida o'sma paydo bo'lib, engil shikastlanadi va sut bezidan qon aralash suyuqlik chiqib turadi yoki ba'zi bir bemorlarda faqat sut bezi uchi yoki Areola bosilganida paydo bo'ladi. Fibroadenoma- sut bezining xavfsiz o'smalariga kiradi. Sut bezida dumaloq qimirleydigan elastik konsistentsiyali yassi yuzali tuzilma paydo bo'lishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Tugunli mastopatiyalar va Fibroadenoma jarroxlik usuli bilan davolanadi.

Metodologiya. Tadqiqot ko'krak bezi saratoni kasalligining kelib chiqish sabablari (etiologiya), maxalliy biologik va ijtimoiy omillari hamda kasallikni davolash, uning profilaktikasi uchu immunitet tizimini mustahkamlash yo'llarini adabiyotlar tahliliga asoslanib olib borildi. Ko'krakda tugun yoki qattiq massa paydo bo'lishi. Eng keng tarqalgan belgi qo'l bilan paypaslanganda seziladigan tugun. Ko'krak shakli yoki hajmining o'zgarishi. Bir tomonning kattalashishi yoki deformatsiyasi. Teridagi o'zgarishlar, ko'krak terisining qizarishi, qalinlashishi apelsin ko'rinishida bo'lish. Ko'krak bezi saratoni yoki tuxumdon raki irsiy genetik mutatsiyalar bilan bog'liq. Masalan: BRCA1 va BRCA2 genlaridagi o'zgarishlar bilan bog'liq.

Immunologik tizim juda noyob, murakkab jarayonlarni mukammal ravishda amalga oshiradigan tizim bo'lib, uning asosiy vazifasi organizmga turli yo'l bilan kirib olgan mikroblar, virus va soda xayvon hujayralarini aniqlab, ularni organizmdan chiqarib yuborishdan iborat. Immunologik tizimning yana bir muhim fazilati bu organizmning o'zida hosil bo'lgan 'nomaqul' tuzilmalarni (autoantigen) aniqlash va ulardan organizmni tozalash qobiliyatini mujassamlashidir.

Immunoterapiya usuli saraton kasalliklarida immunitetni oshirish o'smaga qarshi immunitetni oshirish, o'simta hujayralarining transformatsiyasini kamaytirish va differentsiatsiyasini kuchaytirish, normal tana hujayralarining sitostatik moddalarning zararli ta'siriga toqat qilish qobiliyatini oshirish uchun keng qo'llaniladi va hokazo. Xuddi shunday ta'sirga ega 50 dan ortiq immunomodulyatorlar onkologik amaliyotda va xususan, ko'krak bezi saratonini davolashda qo'llaniladi. Kimyoterapiya usuli ko'krak bezi saratonini tajavuzkor o'simtadir, shuning uchun ko'pchilik kimyoterapiya dorilariga juda sezgir. Qoida tariqasida, ko'krak bezi saratonini davolashda poliximoterapiya qo'llaniladi, chunki har xil faza o'ziga hosligi bo'lgan dorilarning kombinatsiyasi terapevtik ta'sirni kuchaytiradi. Kimyoterapiya ta'siri va vazifasi, bu onkologik hujayralarini o'ldirish yoki ularning ko'payishini to'xtatish. Kimyoterapiya vositalari va ularning ta'siri: Alkillovchi moddalar: DNKni buzadi va hujayraning ko'payishini to'xtatadi. Antimetabolitlar: DNK va RNK sintezini bloklaydi. Taxanlar va antratsiklinlar mitozni to'xtatish orqali ta'sir qiladi (Glibochko P. 2008).

Ko'krak bezi saratonini kasalligi profilaktikasi. Ko'krak bezi saratonining oldini olish birlamchi, ikkilamchi va uchlamchi darajaga bo'linadi. Birlamchi profilaktika: bu kasallikning etiologik va xavf omillarini o'rganish, atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish va kanserogenlarning inson organizimiga ta'sirini kamaytirish, oilaviy hayotni va jinsiy hayotni normallashtirish, tug'ish funksiyasini o'z vaqtida bajarish, chaqaloqni emizishdir. Ikkilamchi profilaktika: mastopatiyaning prekanserov turli shakllarini fibroadenomalarini sut bezi kasalliklarini, shuningdek endokrin bezlari kasalliklarini va boshqa yaxshi o'smalar va tizimning buzilishlarini ayol jinsiy a'zolarining kasalliklarining, jigar disfunktsiyasini erta aniqlash va davolash. Uchunchi darajali profilaktika: bu relapslar metastazlar va metaxron neoplazmalarini oldini olish, erta tashxislash va davolash (Fazliyev Sh va bosh. 2023).

Xulosa: Ko'krak bezi saratonini profelaktikasida immun tizimi muxim ro'l o'ynaydi. Kuchli immunitet organizmning o'sma hujayralarini erta aniqlashi va yo'q qilishi orqali saraton rivojlanish xavfini kamaytiradi. Shuningdek, muntazam tibbiy ko'riklardan o'tish va o'z vaqtida vaksinalar qabul qilish ko'krak bezi saratonining oldini olishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Tavsiyalar: 1) Immunitetni ko'tarish uchun

1 choy qoshiq kurkuma

1 choy qoshiq zanjabil

1 ta lemondi 3-4 bo'lakka bo'lib hammasini idishga solib ustidan 100 gr qaynoq suv quyib yaxshilab aralashtirib och qoringa ertalab ichiladi.

2) Limon po'sti saratonga qarshi kurashadi, undan foydalanish uchun lemon po'stini maydalab ovqatingizga qo'shib iste'mol qiling.

3) Har kuni ertalab och qoringa 1 choy qoshiq asal iste'mol qilish ko'krak bezi saratoni xujayralariga qarshi ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Bundan tashqari ushbu kasallikda muntazam sport bilan shug'illanish tavsiya qilinadi.

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Scientific-methodical journal “Research and implementation”

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<https://rai-journal.uz/>

The Scientific-methodical journal “Research and implementation” was founded by LLC Fer-Teach and supports by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

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